

The Impact of Organizational Values on Employee Performance at Multimedia University of Kenya

Macdonald Ouko Ogambi, MA Graduate, Multimedia University of Kenya

Okumu Collince, Okumu Collince, PhD Student, University of Nairobi

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Abstract

Most organizations prioritized intrinsic and extrinsic reward systems while neglecting the impact of traditional cultural activities. The study therefore sought to assess the impact of organizational culture on employee performance at Multimedia University of Kenya (MMU). The study was guided by the following specific objectives: to determine the impact of organizational values, leadership styles, and work processes on employee performance at Multimedia University of Kenya. The study was anchored on William Ouchi's Theory Z. The study used the descriptive mixed design where a questionnaire and an interview guide was used to collect primary data from key respondents composed of non-teaching staff, academic staff and spread across different departments at MMU. Stratified sampling was used to select the study respondents where a sample size of 194 respondents were used. Out of the sample size, 8 informants all of whom were heads of departments were selected to respond to the interview questions based on their expertise in the study area. The collected data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential analysis tools. Findings of the study revealed a strong and positive relationship between organizational values and employee performance at MMU. The data analysis revealed that specific aspects of organizational culture, including teamwork, recognition, and alignment with organizational values, have a significant impact on employee performance. The study further revealed organizational culture in MMU, characterized by a focus on innovation, quality, and teamwork. The results also highlighted the critical role of leadership in shaping the organizational environment, employee attitudes, and ultimately impacting their performance. The study recommended that given the significant impact of leadership styles on employee performance, the university should invest in leadership development programs. These programs can focus on enhancing communication skills, fostering collaboration, and instilling a leadership philosophy that aligns with the desired organizational culture. Leadership workshops and training sessions can be designed to empower leaders with the necessary skills to positively impact the organizational environment. The study further recommended that the university should prioritize clear and open communication channels, ensuring that information about organizational values, expectations, and achievements is effectively disseminated. Implementing regular feedback mechanisms and encouraging two-way communication can further strengthen the impact of communication on shaping a positive culture.

Keywords: Organizational Values, Employee Performance, Organizational Culture, Multimedia University of Kenya, Innovation, Teamwork, Quality.

Introduction

Organizational culture is a relatively uniform perception held by the organization characterized by; uniqueness, descriptive, individuals' integration, organizational and group variables (Allaire, 2009). In order to aid long term performance, there are three main criteria needed to develop a suitable culture: It must be strategically relevant; it needs to be strong in order for people can care about what is important; and the culture must have an ability to adapt to changing circumstances (Muya & Wasonga 2012). In defining organization culture Comrad (1990) makes two important points that are relevant to the communicative organization. Comrad (1990) points out that organization cultures are communicative creations and historical. Organization culture as a communicative creation does not exist separate from organizational members. Culture is created, sustained, and influenced by and through human interaction. In telling stories, writing memos, having meetings, conducting rites and rituals and other communicative actions, members develop and articulate the central cultural values.

Organizational culture influences communication of its members. Organization members communicate based on the values and interpretive frameworks of the culture, thereby legitimizing use of specialized language, appropriate media for communication, and the conventions of who talks to whom about what, thus reciprocal relationship established.

According to Udegbe et al. (2016), organizational culture performs four functions: gives members a sense of identity, increases commitment, reinforces organizational values and serves as a control mechanism for shaping behavior. There are four important elements of organizational culture that have been key determinants of employee performance i.e., work process, leadership style, organizational value system, and climate (Žugaj & Cingula, 1992). Organizational culture encompasses the unique value systems that define a firm and support its successful operation. Through organizational culture, employees adequately understand the norms, regulations, and value systems underlying the firm. Agwu (2014) noted that organizational culture has remarkable effect on employee's commitment and performance, asserting that a well-understood culture improves employee job satisfaction.

According to Multimedia University strategic plan 2017, MMU was founded in the year 1948 as Central Training School to serve as East African Post Training School before rebranding to Kenya Posts and Telecom Corporation (KPTC). These transitions have resulted to a change of leadership, policies and even the workforce and in one way or the other the organisational culture of the Multimedia University of Kenya hence the motivation of this study. From the MMU's strategic plan it is established that the culture of Multimedia University of Kenya can emanates from among other things the university motto, vision, mission, core values and philosophy. The motto, *Riding on Technology, Inspiring Innovation* points at the institutions focus on the use of technology in its operations while at the same time encouraging innovation. The mission, *to provide quality training, nurture a culture of research, innovation and extension to meet the aspiration of a dynamic society* shows the university focuses on quality training anchored on research, innovation and extension in its effort to meet the ever changing needs of the society.

Multimedia University of Kenya is guided by their core values which are: professionalism, teamwork, adaptation, customer focus, integrity, equity and scholarly values. Apart from the motto, vision, and core values, Multimedia University of Kenya's philosophy is to provide high quality and relevant academic and professional training, to the society as well as human wellbeing, provide the most adaptable and suitable means to improve the social, moral, economic and professional status of an individual being and the whole society, link and correlate the relationship between education, knowledge, faith and reason as a matrix for enhancing better human interactions and society and to develop modern trends that are fully dependent on emerging technologies and changing society norms. The philosophy emphasises the university's focus on the use of technology while focusing on the wellbeing of individuals wellbeing as well as the society.

The main objective of this study was to assess the impact of organizational culture on employee performance at Multimedia University of Kenya, specifically to determine the impact of organizational values on employee performance.

Literature Review

Enz (1988) described organizational values as beliefs that define an individual or group that determine the means to which an underlying organization operates. Such values dictate the actions undertaken by the respective firms to result in the desired performance levels, and are always unique to a particular firm. The organizational values constitute the ideas and beliefs on the target outcomes as dictated by the objectives and which guiding principles should be followed by all organization stakeholders to achieve such defined operation outcomes both in the short and long- runs. Organizational values develop organizational norms, guidelines, or expectations that prescribe appropriate kinds of behavior by employees in particular situations and control the behavior of organizational members towards one another (Black, 2003).

Organizational values can also be defined as beliefs and ideas about the type of goals to be achieved by organizational members and ideas concerning the appropriate types of behavior standards that should be adhered to for goals to be achieved (Sikavica et al., 2008). Organizational Values explain what the organization stands for and beliefs which in effect guide organizational behavior and decisions (Walter, 1995; Johnson, 2009). Values have a long tradition of being associated with shaping, directing and guiding human behavior in and out of organizations. (Box, et al.,1991; Hofstede 1980). In fact, there is growing evidence to suggest that values within

an organization will directly influence an individual to behave in ways that support the organization's goals and objectives (Meglino, et al., 1989). A strong and salient cultural system facilitates the efficient achievement of organizational strategic goals and objectives (Holt 1996). Seeveres (2000) stresses the importance of good communication when defining organizational values by saying that organizational values directly influence the way how people perform their tasks; thus making poor efforts at discussing organizational values can result in decreasing performance of employees and company.

Innovation refers to changes in the structures and processes of an organization that result from developing and implementing new structural, managerial and working concepts and practices to offer the consumer more efficient, effective and flexible solutions (Armbruster et al., 2006). At the firm level, innovation is usually defined as the adoption of an idea or behaviour, pertaining to a product, service, device, system, policy, or programme, that is new to the adopting organization (Daft, 1982; Damanpour & Evan, 1984; Zaltman et al., 1973). Several authors have documented how employees' performance is influenced by innovation through employees generation of ideas for new products and services that eventually improve competitiveness (Sadikoglu & Zehir, 2010), improve administrative process, increase efficiencies and effective work management (Walker et al., 2010), increase organizational fitness (Choi et al., 2009), improve quality performance (Sadikoglu & Zehir, 2010) leading to productivity enhancement (Rostami & Branch, 2011). Moreover, it has been noted that innovation increases the quantity, quality and timeliness of output, job attendance, efficiency and effectiveness of work completed (Tinofirei, 2011).

Sahney, et al., (2004) describes quality using two perspectives, either as attributed to the characteristics of a commodity or its production and delivery (Sahney et al., 2004) also include the importance of meeting and exceeding the expectations of the customers and the need to create customer satisfaction in the goods and services produced and/or delivered. Brooks (2005) finds that quality depends on the organization's purpose, customer base and other contextual factors. Sower and Fair (2006) have found that the traditional definitions and dimensions of quality do not apply to innovative products or paradigm-shifting products or services. For example, in education, quality is viewed as an outcome assessment (Ewell 1994) but also includes a strong stakeholder focus (Telford & Masson, 2005). Telford and Masson (2005) found that quality in higher education must include the criteria and perspectives of all the institutions stakeholders, such as; students, employers, teaching and non-teaching staff, government and its funding agencies, creditors, valuers, auditors, assessors, and the community at large.

Teamwork is the logical and passionate concern of persons in team positions that stimulate them to assist everyone for realizing team objectives and contribute to the job obligation (Gibbon et al., 2002). The efficiency and effectiveness of working groups require motivation and devotion which comes from teamwork spirit (Gibbon et al., 2002; Hardstone et al., 2004) with the intention of facilitating the participants to perform team tasks and group work. Teamwork concerns enhancement in manpower capacity where the target is to increase performance outcomes of both the group and the individual in such teams that achieve thorough collaboration relationships. Thus, employees who work in teams become the standard for the organization (Alie et al., 1998). Research has shown that employee output is enhanced in team works especially where the management accords such groups maximum support. Managers are increasingly assigning more team projects to employees with opportunities to strengthen their knowledge and develop their skills (Hartenian, 2003). Teamwork has the potential of improving the performance of individual employees and the organization, though it needs to be nurtured over time (Ingram, 2000).

Teamwork significantly enhances the smooth functioning of an organization which is a critical component of modern organizations' operation due to the complex nature of such activities underlying a firm. One research study concluded that teamwork is necessary for all types of organization including non-profit organizations (Pfaff & Huddleston, 2003). Performance, greater productivity and better problem solving at work (Cohen & Bailey, 1999). In light of the dynamic business environment, organizations need to consider adequate strategies to enhance their survival. Top management should focus on integrating the organization's vision into the teamwork activities and provide a conducive environment that encourages its flourish for the improved operating outcome of the organization. Conti and Kleiner (2003) reported that teams offer greater participation, challenges and

feelings of accomplishment. Organizations characterized by adequate team development attract and retain best employees who are critical in the organization's competitiveness.

Organizational values are crucial in shaping company culture and can significantly impact performance. According to Fitzgerald & Desjardins (2004), top-performing companies often adhere closely to their core values, and their performance improves when these values are effectively communicated and embraced by employees. Organizational culture is significantly influenced by the organizational value system. These values ultimately shape customer perceptions, how stakeholders are regarded and rewarded, and management of future uncertainties. Such values play a critical role in determining an organization's success (Odom & Dunn, 1991), serving as standards that guide employee performance in various contexts.

Several authors have discussed this phenomenon; Berkhout and Rowlands (2007) conducted a research on personal and organizational values among employees of organizations that specialize in alternative energy sources (solar electricity, wind electricity, smaller hydro-electrical plants, they determined, that those organizations that focus their selection procedure on matching personal values with organizational values tend to be significantly more successful in their work because of the fact that employees have a higher level of job satisfaction. Some later studies in the similar conducted by Kaye and Jordan-Evans (2009) determined that some individuals even perceive the importance of a good match between organizational and personal values to be more important than the income they get.

Organizational values and employee performance linkage is critical in shaping the culture and success of an organization. Organizational values represent the core principles and beliefs that guide behavior and decision-making within the company. When employees align with these values, their performance is often enhanced, as they are more motivated, committed, and engaged in their work (Paarlberg & Perry, 2007). Values such as integrity, teamwork, and innovation provide a framework that influences employee behavior and fosters a positive work environment. Research shows that when employees share and embody organizational values, they experience a greater sense of purpose, leading to improved performance, higher job satisfaction, and lower turnover rates (Chowdhury, 2013). Values alignment helps employees understand the organization's goals, which in turn drives better decision-making and collaboration.

Moreover, organizational values contribute to creating a cohesive culture that encourages employees to perform at their best. Employees who resonate with the organization's values are more likely to exhibit discretionary effort, going beyond the minimum required tasks to contribute to the organization's success (Cameron & Quinn, 2011). Values-driven organizations also see a higher level of accountability, where employees feel responsible not only for their own performance but also for the collective success of the organization. Notably, organizational values are foundational in influencing employee performance by fostering engagement, motivation, and a shared sense of purpose, leading to enhanced overall performance.

Methodology

The adopted methods including design used, study site and population, sampling, data collection, analysis, presentation, ethical considerations, pilot study, and validity of the research instrument are explained in this section. Convergent parallel mixed design with a descriptive approach was used for the study. Kothari (2004) recommends this design because of its characteristics of allowing recording, analysis, reporting, as well as portrayal of conditions which exist. Nachmias and Nachmias (2007) postulates that a descriptive research design is used to obtain information on the position of phenomena to describe what exists with respect to variables in a situation, by asking individuals about their perceptions, attitudes, behavior, values or opinions. This research design helped the researcher understand opinions and perceptions of the respondents on how the organization culture affects employee performance at MMU.

The study was conducted at the Multimedia University of Kenya which is one of the 35 chartered Public Universities according to the Commission for University Education website 2024. According to figures from the Multimedia University of Kenya Human Resource department, the university has 378 employees, who are the target population, 264 are administrative staff while the remaining 114 are academic staff. A sampling frame is a

complete list of all the cases in the population from which a sample size is drawn (Saunders et al., 2009). The sampling frame included staff obtained from the Human Resource department at the Multimedia University of Kenya. The study employed stratified random sampling as a probability sampling method. The researcher settled on this because of its high accuracy level as well as avoidance of bias as compared to simple random sampling technique (Chatterjee & Diaconis, 2018). The respondents were divided into 39 stratus of administrative and academic staff at Multimedia University of Kenya. This was after the population which is 378 is defined, deciding on the relevant sample size for each stratum and randomly sampling from each stratum by calculating the mean, median, and mode of each stratum and comparing them to identify patterns or differences between groups. The researcher employed a non-probability sampling method, which is purposive sampling. The eight heads of department were selected so as to include only subjects that would provide useful data.

According to Mugenda and Mugenda (2003), a sample size of 30% of the population is representative of the population. To ensure accuracy of estimate, a confidence of 95 percent was used in sampling. This means that the accuracy of results is estimated in terms of confidence level where it indicates a degree of certainty and falls within a given range of values (Wimmer & Dominick, 2011). 194 respondents were sampled from a population of 378 MMU members of staff. The study employed the Slovin (1960) formula to determine the sample size.

Survey method was adopted to collect qualitative data. Semi-structured questions were used in this study because they offered an increased response rate and are easily coded and analyzed, while open ended questions are useful in providing more information because they enable respondents to express their thoughts freely and spontaneously (Saunders et al., 2005). Besides the questionnaires, interviews were conducted to collect qualitative data from key informants. These interviews were conducted face to face. Telephone and online meetings were held because of the researcher's physical disability. The interviews were scheduled in advance with time adhered to. All the interview sessions each lasting 20 minutes were recorded on tape with permission from the interviewees. Primary data was collected through the use of questionnaires and interviews. Closed ended questions, used the five-point Likert-type scale, ranking from 1 (Strongly agree) to 5 (Strongly disagree). Interviews were also conducted with the selected heads of department in the university. The interview guide was used to collect data on research question i to iv. Interviews were conducted with the heads of sections from the various departments.

Before beginning the data collection process, approvals to conduct the research were sought from the MMU as well as the National NACOSTI. The respondents were notified of the purpose of the study and a request to participate in the research made to them. As a result of mobility challenges because of the researcher's physical disability, research assistants helped with physical questionnaires distribution while most of the questionnaires were distributed through the internet. Soft copy questionnaires developed using Google forms and shared through WhatsApp and email. To ensure the researcher achieved an appropriate response rate, follow-ups were done through Short Message Service (SMS), emails and phone calls. Voluntary participation, anonymity, and confidentiality were observed. Similarly, the respondent could withdraw at will and were allowed to conceal information that they considered to be private and sensitive. The researcher used codes instead of the respondents' names to ensure confidentiality. The information provided by one respondent was not exposed or shared with another participant whatsoever and was strictly used for the research. The study was guided by acceptable research standards taking into consideration the respondents rights including recording all interview sessions on tape with permissions from the interviewees.

According to Mugenda and Mugenda (2003), a pilot study with a sample of 10% of the total sample with similar characteristics is appropriate. Pilot testing helps in determining the adequacy of a research instrument to recommend corrective actions before actual research. Cohen et al. (2007) record that a pilot study is in fact an imitation and tryout of the main study. Pilot study was conducted at the Multimedia University of Kenya Julious (2005) noted that a sample size of 12 respondents for a pilot study is ideal. This study, therefore, was pre-tested among 12 respondents who were excluded from the main study. Out of the 12 respondents, 3 interviews were conducted while the remaining 9 questionnaires were distributed to the respondents. Reliability measures a research instrument's adequacy in providing a similar outcome when applied on a different population. It is the degree to which a research instrument produces consistent results or data after repeated trials (Orodho, 2012). Reliability was ascertained using the test-retest procedure which administered the questionnaire to the same target

respondents and comparing the similarity in the findings. The questionnaire was reliable because it achieved the same result while conducting the pilot test on samples in the same study area while observer error will be taken care of by this research through the use of a highly structured interview schedule. Validity concerns with the internal consistency underlying study variables such that relevant outcomes are obtained per objective. According to Mugenda and Mugenda (1999), validity is the accuracy and meaningfulness of explanations, which are based on the research results. Both content and face validities were adopted to measure research instrument validity. Content validity examined the closeness in responses of the study variables to result in relevant outcomes. The validity of this study was also ensured through the selection of the study area, sampling of the respondents, and piloting of the research instrument.

The study assessed the impact of organizational culture on employee performance in MMU. The three aspects that guided this study were organization value, leadership styles and work processes with the aim of understanding how these elements impact employee performance in MMU and eventually make recommendations on how best the three values can be used to influence employee performance positively.

The data gathered was edited and cleaned to eliminate errors, inconsistencies, and outliers for descriptive and inferential statistics. Through coding, the qualitative data was transformed into quantitative information to enable successful analysis using the SPSS Version 26 software. SPSS helped to measure central tendencies; relationship between variables and to what extent independent variables affected the dependent variable. Inferential analysis tools made corollaries about the population from which the sample was selected (Leavy, 2017). Correlation analysis to determine variable relationships constituted the inferential in this study. And results presented in figures and tables. According to Amin (2005) descriptive statistics provides the techniques of numerically and graphically presenting information that gives an overall picture of the data collected. The final constituent in the interview design process was the interpretation of data gathered during the interview process. During this phase, the researcher must make “sense” out of what was just uncovered and compile the data into sections or groups of information, also known as themes or codes (Creswell, 2003, 2007). These themes or codes are consistent phrases, expressions, or ideas that were common among research participants (Kvale, 2007). According to Kvale (1996), a structured interview, which may yield numerical data, can be reported succinctly in tables and graphs, whilst an open-ended interview which would yield word-based accounts, may be presented in the form of narratives.

Results

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean	Std
I fully understand MMU organizational values	34%	36%	20%	7.3%	2.7%	2.087	1.04
I personally uphold these values	36.7%	36.7%	14%	6.7%	2%	1.947	.99
Fellow employees uphold MMU organizational values	9.3%	32%	39.3%	16%	3.3%	2.720	.96
The MMU organizational values guide our behavior and tell us what is right or wrong.	14.6%	41.3%	28%	10%	6%	2.513	1.06
The MMU organizational values dictate how we do our work.	14%	41.3%	25.3%	13.3%	5.3%	2.544	1.06
MMU organizational values impact positively on employee performance	11.3%	29.3%	33.3%	18.7%	7.3%	2.813	1.09
MMU organizational values encourage the creation of new and improved ideas, methods and devices at work.	10%	29.3%	28%	21.3%	10.7%	2.933	1.16
MMU values encourage quality work by employee.	12%	36%	26%	17.3%	8.7%	2.747	1.14

MMU employees endeavor to produce the desired quality and quantity of assignments	Quality work leads to high employee performance	18.7%	42%	23.3%	12%	4%	2.407	1.05
MMU management encourages consultation, teamwork and participation among its employees.		34.7%	37.3%	15.3%	10%	2.7%	2.087	1.07
MMU employees work together well to improve their performance.		6%	24%	29.3%	22%	18.7%	3.233	1.18
Teamwork impacts positively on employee performance		10%	32.7%	28.7%	21.3%	7.3%	2.833	1.10

Table 1: organizational values in MMU: Source: Researcher (2024)

Table 1 indicates the critical role of organizational values in MMU, particularly in terms of organizational values impact on employee performance. The data revealed a range of perspectives among the respondents, with varying levels of agreement and disagreement across the fourteen statements. There is a relatively high percentage of respondents who either strongly agree or agree that they have complete knowledge and understanding of MMU's organizational values and that they personally uphold these values. 34% of the respondents strongly agreed while 36% agreed with this statement. 36.7 % strongly agreed and another 36.7% of the respondents agreed that they had complete knowledge and understanding of MMU organizational values. However, there appeared to be a more diverse range of opinions regarding whether fellow employees upheld MMU's organizational values, 9.3% of the respondents strongly agreed, 32% agreed and a substantial 39.3% remaining neutral.

The findings also highlighted the perceived influence of MMU's organizational values on guiding employee behavior and dictating work processes. 14.6% of the respondents strongly agreed and 41.3% agreed that these values guided what is considered right or wrong. On the other hand, 14% of the respondents strongly agreed and another 41.3% agreed that MMU organizational values dictated how they did their work. Additionally, a considerable percentage 42.7% believed that MMU's organizational values positively impact employee performance with 10% strongly agreeing with the statement while the remaining 32.7% agreeing with the statement. The data also suggested a divided perception regarding the role of MMU's organizational values in encouraging innovation and quality work. 39.3% agreed that these values encouraged the creation of new ideas and methods with 10% strongly agreeing and the remaining 29.3% of the respondents agreed while a notable 32% disagreed .Of that figure, 10.7% of the respondents strongly agreed while the remaining 21.3% disagreed with the statement .Similarly, 48% of respondents agreed that MMU's values encourage quality work, with 12% strongly agreeing with this statement and the remaining 36% agreeing with the statement but a substantial 26% remained neutral on this statement.

The findings also revealed aspects of teamwork and collaboration within MMU. A majority 72% agreed that MMU's management encourages consultation, teamwork, and participation among employees.34.7% strongly agreed with this statement while the remaining 37.3% respondents agreed with the statement. However, there was a more varied response regarding whether employees work together well to improve their performance, with only 30% agreeing. A meager 6% and 24% strongly agreed and agreed with the statements respectively. A significant 40.7% disagreeing or strongly disagreeing. 22% of the respondents agreed with this statement while the other 18.7% strongly disagreed with the statement. From literature, organizations which emphasize more on teams have resulted in increased employee performance, greater productivity and better problem solving at work (Cohen & Bailey, 1999). Therefore, this implies that MMU considerably considers teamwork as an indicator of employee performance by the management encouraging consultation and participation among employees. However, the university needs to work on aspects of teamwork like employees working together well to improve their performance and thus improving the general performance of the university.

The study showed responses to various statements about MMU organizational values and their impact on employee performance. The mean scores range from 1.947 to 3.233 on a 5-point scale, suggesting generally moderate agreement with most statements. The lowest mean (1.947) is for "I personally uphold these values," indicating strong individual commitment to MMU's values therefore resulting in a positive impact on employee

performance. The highest mean (3.233) is for "MMU employees work together well to improve their performance," suggesting more positive views on teamwork effectiveness which meant that the employees valued teamwork and collaboration. Standard deviations range from 0.9562 to 1.1839, indicating variability in responses. The standard deviation (0.9562) is for "Fellow employees uphold MMU organizational values," showing relatively consistent perceptions meaning that a majority of the employees agreed that fellow employees upheld MMU's values. The largest (1.1839) is for the teamwork statement, reflecting more diverse opinions. This variability indicated that respondents had differing perspectives on teamwork, which could suggest varying experiences or interpretations of teamwork within the organization.

Overall, the descriptive statistics presented in Table 4.4 show the perceived impact of MMU's organizational values on employee performance, highlighting areas of strength as well as potential areas for improvement or further exploration. In exploring indicators of innovation at MMU during the interview phase of the study, Informant 3 emphasized the use of technology, research output, industry collaborations, and curriculum review and development as key metrics. According to informant 7, *"Supporting students' innovative projects is considered an indicator of innovation within the university"*. The diverse perspectives on innovation highlight the multi-faceted nature of the term within the institution. Informant 2 also added that: *"Providing opportunities for faculty and staff to engage in continuous professional development can ensure they stay abreast of new methodologies and technologies"*. MMU might organize workshops or training sessions on emerging trends in multimedia technology, enhancing the skills of its workforce.

Regarding the adoption of new ideas, methods, or devices, most informants outlined various approaches. Informant 5 described the involvement of MMU in research and development initiatives, industry partnerships, continuous professional development, and the adoption of e-learning platforms. In contrast, informant 2 expressed a lack of personal experience with such initiatives, pointing to a potential variability in the dissemination of innovative practices across different departments. The impact of new and improved ideas on employee performance was articulated positively by informant 1, citing enhancements in teaching and learning experiences, professional development opportunities, career advancement, and student engagement. Another informant was in support by saying that, *"Well an example for me is the ease of exam processing through the system which has made my work as the chair of the department much simpler."* However, informant 4 claimed to be unaware of such impacts, underlining potential communication gaps or varied experiences among employees.

In terms of quality indicators, most informants highlighted factors like customer satisfaction, process efficiency, timeliness, and feedback. The emphasis on offering services within the required time frame was noted as a quality indicator by informant 6. Informant 3 said, *"Challenges influencing quality performance such as a lack of patriotism to the university and low morale among employees"*. Informant 7 also added that, *"When employees contribute to delivering high-quality products or services, they often develop a sense of purpose and pride in their work."*

Teamwork was assessed through indicators like team meetings, interdepartmental communication, and cross-functional training. This contributed positively to employee performance. Informant 1 expressed, *"The practice of involving members in decision-making as a manifestation of teamwork, asserting that teamwork enhances ownership and self-worth"*. The study established a strong positive correlation between organizational values and employee performance. This aligns with existing literature that emphasizes the significant impact of organizational culture on various aspects of employee behaviours, motivation, and job satisfaction (Younies & Al-Tawil, 2021).

Summary, Conclusion, And Recommendations

The study's findings underscored a strong and positive relationship between organizational values and employee performance at MMU. The data analysis revealed that specific aspects of organizational culture, including teamwork, recognition, and alignment with organizational values, enhance employee performance. MMU culture, characterized by a focus on innovation, quality, and teamwork, contributes to an environment that enhances employees' work quantity, quality, independence, timeliness, relationships, job satisfaction, and commitment.

The results affirm the crucial role of a well-defined and positively oriented organizational culture in fostering an atmosphere conducive to optimal employee performance within the university setting.

The study revealed that organizational values play a pivotal role in shaping employee performance at MMU. The analysis indicated a positive correlation between organizational values and various dimensions of employee performance, such as work quality, work quantity, and commitment. Employees who perceive a clear alignment between their actions and the organization's values tend to exhibit higher job satisfaction and engagement. The findings suggest that MMU's emphasis on values such as innovation, quality, and teamwork significantly contributes to fostering a positive work environment, ultimately enhancing employee performance.

The findings showed a strong positive correlation between organizational culture and employee performance shedding light on the pivotal role organizational culture plays in shaping employee behaviours, motivation, and overall employee performance within the university context. Organizational culture, defined by shared values, beliefs, and norms, is revealed as a strong indicator of employee performance at MMU. The positive correlation signifies that a strong and positive organizational culture motivates employees to achieve values and goals of the institution. The findings reveal the crucial role of leadership in shaping the overall work environment, underscoring how clear leadership styles contribute to the development of employee performance. The analysis reveals a significant positive correlation between leadership styles and employee performance at MMU.

This suggests that the leadership approach adopted within the university, encompassing aspects such as communication, decision-making, and team collaboration define prevailing organizational culture. Leadership with clear communication, trust-building, and the encouragement of employee involvement, is identified as a catalyst for a positive organizational culture. Leaders who prioritize these qualities contribute to an atmosphere where employees are engaged, motivated, and aligned with firm values. This aligns with leadership theories on the role of transformative and participative leadership styles in creating a conducive work environment. The findings provide a comprehensive understanding of how the efficiency and effectiveness of work processes contribute to the establishment of a positive employee performance.

The study recommends that the university should prioritize clear and open communication channels, ensuring that information about organizational values, expectations, and achievements is effectively disseminated. Implementing regular feedback mechanisms and encouraging two-way communication can further strengthen the impact of communication on shaping a positive culture.

References

- Agwu, M.O. (2014). Organizational culture and employees' performance in the National Agency for Food and Drugs Administration and Control (NAFDAC) Nigeria. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*, 14(2), 1- 9.
- Ahmad, S. M. (2012). Impact of organizational culture on performance Management Practices in Pakistan. *Business Intelligence Journal*, 5(1), 50-52.
- Allaire Y., & Firsirontu, E. (1984). Theories of organizational culture. *Organization Studies*, 5(3), 193-226.
- Aluko, M. 2003. The Impact of Culture on Organizational performance in Selected Textile Firms in Nigeria. *Nordic Journal of African Studies*. 12.(2), 164–179.
- Atiku, S. O., Fields, Z. & Abe, E. (2017). Cultural values and human resource outcomes in the Nigerian banking industry. *SPOUDAI- Journal of Economics and Business*, 67(2), 26-46.
- Black, R. J. (2003). *Organizational culture: creating the influence needed for strategic success*. Universal-Publishers.

- Box, W. R., Odom, R. Y., & Dunn, M. G. (1991). Organizational values and value congruency and their impact on satisfaction, commitment, and cohesion: An empirical examination within the Public Sector. *Public Personnel Management* 20(1), 195–205.
- Deal, T. E., & Kennedy, A. A. (1982). *Corporate cultures: The rites and rituals of corporate life*. Addison-Wesley Publishing Company.
- Enz, C. A. (1988). The role of value congruity in intra-organizational power. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 33(2), 284-304.
- Geertz, C. (1973). *The interpretation of cultures*. Basic Books, Inc., Publishers.
- Johnson, K. M. (2009). *The influence of organizational values on profitability*. [Doctoral dissertation, Auburn University].
- Mckinono, F. (2003). The effects of organizational culture on employee psychological attachment. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 15(2)126-146.
- Munyambu, J. (2015). *Relationship between Culture and Performance: A Case Study of Del Monte Kenya Limited*. *International Journal of Management and Commerce Innovation*, 3(1), 274- 291
- Muya J. N., & Wesonga, J. N. (2012). The Impact of organizational culture on performance of educational institutions. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 3(8), 211-217.
- Multimedia University of Kenya. (2017). *Strategic Plan (2017-2021)*.
- Omega P, M. (2012). *The perceived relationship between organizational culture and employees' job satisfaction at Kenya Commercial Bank*. [Master's Thesis, University of Nairobi].
- Onyango, D, O. (2014). *The influence of organizational culture on employee job performance: A case study of Pacis Insurance Company Limited*. [Master's Thesis, United States International University, Africa].
- Pacanowsky, M., & O'Donnell-Trujillo, N. (1983). Organizational communication as cultural performance. *Communication Monographs*, 50, 126-147.
- Pathiranage, Y. L., Jayatilake, L. V., & Abeysekera, R. (2020). Case study research design for exploration of organizational culture towards corporate performance. *Review of International Comparative Management/Revista de Management Comparat International*, 21(3), 361-372.
- Ravasi, D., & Schultz, M. (2006). Responding to organizational identity threats: exploring the role of organizational culture. *Academy of Management Journal*, 49(3), 433–458.
- Udegbe, S. E., Afobunor, S. A. & Udegbe, M. I. (2016). Exploring the relationship among organizational culture, customer satisfaction and performance in multinational corporations in Nigeria. *Australian Journal of Business and Management Research*, 1(11), 78-92.
- Udin, M. J., Luva, H., & Hossan, M. (2013). Impact of Organizational Culture on Employee Performance and Productivity: A Case Study of Telecommunication Sector in Bangladesh. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 8(2), 63.
- Ouchi, W. G. (1981). *Theory Z: How American business can meet the Japanese challenge*. Addison-Wesley Pub (Sd).

- Kothari, C. R. (2004). *Research Methodology: Methods and Techniques* (3rd ed.). New York: New Age International.
- Mugenda, O. M., & Mugenda, A. G. (2003). *Research methods: quantitative and qualitative approaches*. Acts press.
- Orodho J. A. (2002). *Techniques of Writing Research Proposals and Reports in Education and Social Sciences*. Masola Publishers.
- Saunders, M., Lewis, P., & Thornhill, A. (2009). *Research Methods for Business Students*. Financial Times Prentice Hall.
- Wimmer, R. D., & Dominick, J. R. (2011). *Mass Media Research: An Introduction* (9th Ed.). Wadsworth Cengage Learning.
- Julious, S. A. (2005). Sample size per group rule of thumb for a pilot study. *The Journal of Applied Studies in the Pharmaceutical Industry*,4(4),287-291.